

ECRs, publish your datasets and methods as mini-papers

Do you have useful datasets and methods? Consider publishing them as “mini-papers” prior to formal publication in a journal.

. . .

“Mini-papers” are the underrated scholarly outputs of academia. For many Early Career Researchers (ECRs), publishing a full fledged research article is a daunting task. So, why not break down this task into smaller, less intimidating units and publish them as datasets or method papers?

We had a real case example with Thorsten Langner et al. paper on mini-chromosomes of the blast fungus (*Magnaporthe oryzae*) that was ultimately published in early 2021 in PLOS Genetics.

The paper builds on three different pre-publications that served as milestones in this scientific publishing journey.

First, the nanopore sequencing of genomic DNA from *M. oryzae* isolates was posted on Zenodo in February 2019. Zenodo is an open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE initiative. This Win et al. Technical Note provides the metadata and genome sequencing details of Thorsten’s paper. It is cited as reference 57 in the PLOS Genetics paper.

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February 14, 2019 Technical note Open Access

Nanopore sequencing of genomic DNA from *Magnaporthe oryzae* isolates from different hosts

Joe Win; Emilie Chanclud; C. Sarai Reyes-Avila; Thorsten Langner; Tofazzal Islam; Sophien Kamoun

We report long-range sequencing of eight isolates of *Magnaporthe oryzae* (Syn. *Pyricularia oryzae*) from wheat, rice, foxtail millet and goosegrass using nanopore MinION. Our aim is to obtain chromosome-level genome assemblies that are freely available for public access to be scrutinized for genome rearrangements and structural variation.

Magnaporthe oryzae (Syn. *Pyricularia oryzae*) is a notorious fungus known for causing blast disease on rice and wheat with devastating effect on grain yield. *M. oryzae* host range includes several other cereal crops such as oat, finger millet and foxtail millet as well as wild grasses. *M. oryzae* is found all over the world wherever warm temperature and high humidity are common. Although lineages of *M. oryzae* tend to be adapted to a particular host, this pathogen can shift from one host to another when the conditions permit (Couch *et al.* 2005). We hypothesize that structural variation contributes to adaptation to new hosts and environmental conditions following, for example, the model proposed by Chuma *et al.* (2011). To generate the genomics data that would enable such analyses, we sequenced eight isolates of *M. oryzae* from four different hosts using long-range nanopore MinION with the aim of providing chromosome-level genome assemblies that are freely available for public access.

Win et al. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2564950>

Second, the method and protocol for mini-chromosome isolation and sequencing described in Langner et al. was first published in November 2019 in another platform [protocols.io](https://www.protocols.io), which promotes sharing and discussion of reproducible methods. This [protocols.io](https://www.protocols.io) article was also [cited in the PLOS Genetics paper as reference 75](#)

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Isolation of supernumerary mini-chromosomes from fungi for enrichment sequencing

PLOS Genetics

Thorsten Langner¹, Adeline Harant¹, Sophien Kamoun¹

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Dec 17, 2019

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Thorsten Langner

Langner, T. et al. 2019 <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.9t7h6rn>

Finally, an earlier version of the paper itself was published [as a preprint in the bioRxiv server in January 2020](#), more than a year before the PLOS Genetics paper went online.

bioRxiv posts many COVID19-related papers. A reminder: they have not been formally peer-reviewed and should not guide health-related behavior or be reported in the press as conclusive.

New Results

Follow this preprint

Genomic rearrangements generate hypervariable mini-chromosomes in host-specific lineages of the blast fungus

Thorsten Langner, Adeline Harant, Luis B. Gomez-Luciano, Ram K. Shrestha, Joe Win, Sophien Kamoun

doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.01.10.901983>

Langner et al. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.01.10.901983>

Thorsten happily tweeted a paper thread about the paper in January 2020, again over one year before the journal article was posted.

Paper threads are the latest academic publishing genre and you can find here my tips about writing them. They can definitely expand the reach of your science beyond your immediate academic network. Thorsten's preprint and tweet were widely shared on social media and helped promote his work months before journal publication. No wonder the preprint movement is known as ASAPbio.

One common and important factor in the three pre-publications mentioned above is that they all include a doi—a digital object identifier. This is important as it makes your scholarly product

permanent and unambiguous in the internet, therefore the work can be cited with confidence. A blog post like this one for example, can be modified even years after publishing. Assigning your work to a DOI doesn't allow you to do that, and this is critical for scientific discourse. Note, however, that you can still post additional versions or revisions of your DOI article.

doi: digital object identifier

What is a DOI and how do I use them in citations?

A DOI, or Digital Object Identifier, is a string of numbers, letters and symbols used to permanently identify an article or document and link to it on the web. A DOI will help your reader easily locate a document from your citation.

WHAT IS A DOI?

DOI stands for Digital Object Identifier.

A DOI is a standardized system for identifying an electronic or digital object.

A DOI looks like this:

DOI: 10.1080/15575330903279630

The DOI System

I often get the question of whether posting these mini-papers and preprints will prevent from publishing later on in a journal. The answer is obviously no given the example above. Pretty much all academic publishers these days accept preprints. [Check all the green “unrestricted” on this wikipedia page.](#) It wasn't always like that, but the scientific publishing world has been somehow adjusting to the digital age, and the popular preprint movement is irresistible.

It goes without saying that posting mini-papers and preprints will help beef up an ECR's CV. It gives your potential employers and fellowship reviewers some concrete outputs to evaluate you months before your work makes it into journals. In addition, your peers will get to know you and benefit from your resources. Hey, you may become popular as that nice person who shared early on their invaluable datasets and knowledge.

Check for instance this amazing [18 new aphid genome assemblies that were made available to the community through a Zenodo paper](#). In just one go, [Tom Mathers](#) and colleagues at the John Innes Centre more than doubled the number of available genomes of this fascinating insect pest. I'm sure this can only help advance Tom's career and gain him further exposure among his peers. The last I checked the Zenodo article had ~500 page views just a couple of days after posting.

Tom Mathers

@Thomas_Mathers

Excited to announce the release of 18 new [#aphid](#) genome assemblies (8 chromosome-scale) with [@SaskiaHogehout](#) and others.

We are making the genomes and annotations available ahead of publication without restriction.

So, consider doing your bit to help transition academic publishing into the open science era. Share your datasets and methods as doi in Zenodo or other platforms in a way that gives you full credit and will not prevent from formally publishing in journals. Scholarly outputs aren't just journal articles and engaging with the wider community can make a big difference for early career scientists. It's all part of the perspective that you will be eventually judged as a scientist for your varied and original outputs, rather than some silly metrics. Check [Yasin Dagdas'](#) inspiring thread on academic job interviews, and consider how mini-papers would fit in your career narrative.

Yasin Dagdas

@PlantoPhagy

Having observed a series of academic job interviews lately, here is a short thread (as usual always take them with a grain of salt & sorry for the GIF abuse)1/6

Watch on Twitter